

Developer Experience Questionnaire

Pre-Questionnaire

- 1) What is your profession/job title?
- 2) How many people, approximately, do you coordinate your work with on a regular basis?
 - No one (I do not need to coordinate my work)
 - 2 people
 - 3-5 people
 - 6-14 people
 - 15-29 people
 - 30 or more people
- 3) Do you have any people reporting to you?
 - Yes
 - No
- 4) How many people are in the space/office you are currently working in?
 - 1 person (just me)
 - 2 people
 - 3-5 people
 - 6-14 people
 - 15 or more people
- 5) Do you work remotely?
 - Never
 - I rarely work remotely
 - Part-time remote – Write In the percentage of remote work during a week: ____
 - Full-time remote
 - Other – Write In: _____
- 6) We want to get a sense of your typical work week. In the table below, please enter roughly how many hours per week you spend on each of the activities. If there are activities that you think should be included, please list them at the bottom of the table in the row “Enter another option”.

	Hours spent per week
Writing code	
Debugging or fixing bugs	
Running tests on code	
Meetings	
Email	
Helping/Mentoring	
Working on/with specs/requirements	
Reviewing code	
Documentation	
Enter another option	

Honing skills/Continuous learning	
Administrative tasks	
Networking/Maintaining relationships	
Enter another option: _____	

- 7) How many years of IT or programming experience do you have?
- 1 year or less
 - Between 1 and 2 years
 - Between 2 and 5 years
 - Between 5 and 10 years
 - Between 10 and 20 years
 - More than 20 years
- 8) If applicable, which programming languages do you use?
- 9) Will you participate in the extended version of this study (recording of your working day via a body sensor wristband)?
- yes
 - no
- If yes:
- Handedness
 right left mixed ambidextrous
 - Please specify neurological, psychological or chronic medical conditions if applicable.
 - Please specify which medication you are currently taking if applicable.

Work satisfaction

1) Overall, how satisfied are you with your current job?

- Very dissatisfied
- Dissatisfied
- Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
- Satisfied
- Very satisfied

2) Overall, I feel satisfied with the kind of work I do in this job. (adapted from a 7-point Likert scale to a 5-point Likert scale)

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

3) How much do each of the following challenges impact you?

	Not at all	Very little	Somewhat	To a great extent	Not applicable
My manager					
Poorly defined goals					
Lack of team/organization vision					
Poorly qualified co-workers					
Poor team culture					
Lack of personal technical skills					
Poor software development process					
Poor engineering tools					
Poor hardware resources					
Poor collaboration tools					
Interacting with people					
Too many emails					
Too many meetings					
Too many interruptions					
Too many communication					

channels (email, instant messaging, etc.)					
Lack of quiet space to do work					
Finding enough time to complete my work					
Insufficient training					
Finding information of documentation					
Legacy code					
The development language, platform or stack					
Changing product requirements					
Poor software architecture					
Too many external dependencies					
Other: _____					

DevEx Questionnaire

Flow State

- 1) “My mind isn’t wandering. I am totally involved in what I am doing and I am not thinking of anything else. My body feels good. I don’t seem to hear anything. The world seems to be cut off from me. I am less aware of myself and my problems.” Can you relate to this quote during work?

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Very often
- Always

If you can relate, during which activities do you experience this?

- 2) “I am really quite oblivious to my surroundings after I really get doing in this activity.” Can you relate to this quote during work?

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Very often
- Always

If you can relate, during which activities do you experience this?

- 3) I have a significant amount of time for deep work in my work days.

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Very often
- Always

- 4) In a typical week, how often are you interrupted to work on something else that was unplanned or suddenly requested?

- At least once every couple of hours
- At least once per day
- At least once every two days
- At least once per week
- Less than once per week

- 5) Generally speaking, the coding tasks I work on are more engaging than boring.

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Very often
- Always

Feedback loops

- 6) How often does it take more than 10 minutes to obtain an answer to an internal technical question (i.e. about code, a system, or the domain you are working in)?

- At least once every two days

- At least once per week
 - At least once every two weeks
 - At least once per month
 - Less than once per month
- 7) Approximately what percentage of the code reviews you request are completed within 4 business hours?
- 0 - 20%
 - 21 - 40%
 - 41 - 60%
 - 61 - 80%
 - 81 - 100%

Cognitive load

- 8) For the primary team you work on, how would you rate the ease of deploying changes?
- Very bad
 - Bad
 - Acceptable
 - Good
 - Very good
- 9) How often can you easily understand the code you work with?
- Never
 - Rarely
 - Sometimes
 - Very often
 - Always
- 10) In general, the processes I need to follow to do my work are easy for me to figure out.
- Never
 - Rarely
 - Sometimes
 - Very often
 - Always
- 11) In general, the developer tools I have are intuitive and easy to use.
- Never
 - Rarely
 - Sometimes
 - Very often
 - Always
- 12) How would you rate your overall cognitive load on average on a normal working day?
- Very low
 - Low
 - Neither low nor high
 - High
 - Very high

Developer impacts

- 13) I learned new skills related to my work in the past month.
- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Undecided
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
- 14) I have felt very productive over the past month.
- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Undecided
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
- 15) I have been creative in my work in the past month.
- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Undecided
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree

Team impacts

- 16) How would you rate the quality of the code you work on?
- Very bad
 - Bad
 - Acceptable
 - Good
 - Very good
- 17) How often does technical debt impact your ability to complete new work?
- Always
 - Very often
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
 - Never

Organization impacts

- 18) How often do you look for jobs at other companies? (Again, this question is private and only visible to the research team.)
- Every day
 - Every week
 - Every month
 - Every few months
 - I never look for jobs at other companies
- 19) My company culture supports innovation.
- Strongly disagree

- Disagree
- Undecided
- Agree
- Strongly agree

20) My organization achieves its goals.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Undecided
- Agree
- Strongly agree

21) My organization is profitable.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Undecided
- Agree
- Strongly agree

Perceived workload

22) I feel that the amount of work I do interferes with how well it is done. (adapted from a 7-point Likert scale to a 5-point Likert scale)

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Undecided
- Agree
- Strongly agree

Work exhaustion

23) I feel emotionally drained from my work. (adapted from a 7-point Likert scale to a 5-point Likert scale)

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Undecided
- Agree
- Strongly agree

24) I feel used up at the end of the workday. (adapted from a 7-point Likert scale to a 5-point Likert scale)

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Undecided
- Agree
- Strongly agree

25) I feel burned out from my work. (adapted from a 7-point Likert scale to a 5-point Likert scale)

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree

Undecided

Agree

Strongly agree

26) What could increase your developer experience (i.e. technical/programming features, work coordination, organizational structures etc.)?

References

Forsgren, N., Kalliamvakou, E., Noda, A., Greiler, M., Houck, B., & Storey, M. A. (2023). DevEx in Action: A study of its tangible impacts. *Queue*, 21(6), 47-77.

Moneta, G. B. (2021). On the conceptualization and measurement of flow. In *Advances in flow research* (pp. 31-69). Cham: Springer International Publishing.

Rutner, P. S., Hardgrave, B. C., & McKnight, D. H. (2008). Emotional dissonance and the information technology professional. *Mis Quarterly*, 635-652.

Storey, M. A., Zimmermann, T., Bird, C., Czerwonka, J., Murphy, B., & Kalliamvakou, E. (2019). Supplemental material for towards a theory of software developer job satisfaction and perceived productivity. Available: <https://zenodo.org/record/3451354#.XYUr-OdKjOQ>.